

A Appendix: Example PEM Lesson

Contextual Details:

- Course level/topic: Intro to programming (CS1)
- Prerequisite topics: programming, compiler
- Programming language: C
- Compiler/IDE/Toolchain: GCC

Key points included:

- Vocabulary: error, warning, compiler, message, syntax error, runtime error, logic error, expression, identifier, binary expression, implicit conversion, preprocessor, lexical analyzer, syntactic analyzer, code generator, linker, linker error
- The compiler is deterministic
- Message understanding
- Treat all warnings as errors
- Solve one problem at a time; first error message first
- Take ‘suggestions’ with a grain of salt
- You can ask for help
- examples

Lesson Title: Reading and Using Compiler Messages

Programming Errors

Three kinds of errors are made in programming:

Syntax Error a mistake in the source code of the program that prevents the program from being compiled and run (i.e., the program does not conform to the grammar rules of the language). Compilers detect syntax errors.

Runtime Error a running program can encounter errors for a variety of reasons due to bad input, missing files, or other reasons. Compilers can not detect runtime errors. In this case, the program can compile, and run, but does not run successfully.

Logic Error as it says, a mistake in logic. Programs with logical errors can be compiled, but result in a program that does the wrong thing. Compilers rarely detect logic errors.

A.1 Understanding Compiler Messages

A.1.1 Error Message versus Warning. Compilers produce messages when an error, or possible error, is found in the code it is trying to compile. Compiler messages fall into two categories:

errors when an error exists, the program can not be compiled and a message is produced indicating something about the error.

warnings warning messages indicate a possible error, but the program can be compiled as is. A program compiled with a warning likely has a logic and/or potential runtime error. Warning messages should not be ignored.

The GCC compiler has an option that makes the compiler treat warnings like errors. The **-Werror** option forces the compiler to treat all warnings like errors and when that option is used, the compiler will not compile source code that would have otherwise produces an error message. It is standard practice in this course to compile with the **-Werror** option.

A.1.2 Compiler Message(s) Means a Fix is Needed. When an error message is produced, a problem exists in the code—absolutely. Compiling the code again without making one or more source code edits is pointless and will only result in the exact same error message(s) being produced again.

A.1.3 Error Location. Below is a program and, further below, the resulting compiler message. The program isn’t useful, except to show the error message that results. In the program a capital letter O (Oscar) is where a number is needed (zero would be a good choice). The compiler detected this as an error because O (Oscar) has no meaning in this program, and produced an error message.

```
#include <stdio.h>

int main(void) {
    int sum = 0;
}
```

source code in file example.c

The error message begins with example.c:5:13: error which indicates the problem detected is in the:

- in the file named: example.c
- on line 5
- in column 13
- and is an error

Following those details is a description of the error. On the following line is the line of code, followed by a line with a caret (^) pointing to the character which was read when the compiler detected the problem.

```
example.c:5:13: error: use of undeclared
identifier 'O'
int sum = 0;
           ^
```

error message from source code in file example.c

In the above example, the compiler has identified the exact place an edit is necessary. However, in some cases, the compiler does not detect the actual error. This is particularly true when the source code is missing a delimiter (e.g., quote, parenthesis, curly brace). The programmer’s mistake can be anywhere before the place the compiler detected the error.

A.1.4 The Message. Understanding compiler error messages requires knowing the vocabulary used as well as understanding how errors are detected. Some common error message vocabulary includes:

expression the combination of values (constants or variables) and operators; for example: `A + B`, or `3.14 * radius * radius`.

binary expression an expression, or sub expression, that involves exactly two terms and one operator.

identifier the name of a variable or function.

implicit conversion necessary change of type of a value; for example, in the statement: `int b = 3.14`; it is necessary to

change the value 3.14 to 3 because the variable `b` has type `int` and can not represent the fractional part of 3.14 .

The compiler “knows” nothing about the program you are trying to write; therefore, compiler messages are written only in terms of the source code. Consequently, error messages can be misleading. For example, in the example given above, the compiler reading the letter `O` (Oscar) and determined that `O` is a legal identifier, but compiler found that identifier is not associated with anything (i.e., no declared variable is named `O`). The resulting error message indicates that exact idea: there is no variable named `O` (Oscar). The idea of where messages “come from” is explored in more detail in the next section.

A.2 Compiler Technology and Compiler Messages

Compiling source code into an executable is a complex problem. Complex problems are often decomposed into smaller problems, and the smaller problems are solved independently. When done correctly, the combination of the solutions to the smaller problems form a solution to the larger problem.

The GCC compiler is an example of solving a complex problem with a combination of smaller solutions. In particular, GCC is an example of layered software architecture - a solution to a complex problem that is composed of a several layers of software, in which each layer handles a subset of the problem. At a high-level, the layers of the GCC compiler are:

- **preprocessor** - handles directives, such as `#include` and `#define`; the input to the preprocessor is source code, the output is modified source code
- **lexical analyzer** - reads the source code les as characters and tokens. A token can be a single variable name, operator, or symbol.
- **syntactic analyzer** - reads a string of tokes to ensure they follow the syntax rules (i.e., grammar rules) of the language
- **code generator** - converts a legal the token string into machine code
- **linker** - combines machine code from different les into one executable file

Understanding the inner workings of the compiler can lead to a better understanding of the error and warning messages that it produces. Almost every layer of the compiler can produce an error or warning message.

A.2.1 Preprocessor. This lesson introduced the `#include` and `#define` preprocessor directives. These directives are handled by the preprocessor (the first step in compilation). The preprocessor detects many kinds of errors with preprocessor directives. Errors found by the preprocessor typically are the result of spelling mistakes. The Table below gives two examples of preprocessing errors.

source code	<code>#include <stdio></code>
error message	<code>'stdio' not found</code>
what it means	Filename is spelled incorrectly
fix	<code>#include <stdio.h></code>
source code	<code>#inlud <stdio.h></code>
error message	Invalid preprocessing directive
what it means	<code>#include</code> is spelled incorrectly
fix	<code>#include <stdio.h></code>

An error detected in the preprocessor process stops the compilation. As a result, other errors in the code may not be detected. This can be frustrating when fixing one error and compiling again seems to produce other errors.

A.2.2 Lexical Analysis. The lexical analyzer reads the source code one letter at a time and converts characters into tokens. For example, the character stream `int sum = 0;` would be converted into five tokens “`int`” a type, “`sum`” an identifier (variable name), “`=`” assignment operator, `int` constant 0, and “`;`” semicolon. The lexical analyzer ends a token when a space is read. The lexical analyzer would convert these characters `sum int = 0;` into the same five tokens in a different order: “`sum`” variable name, “`int`” a type, “`=`” assignment operator, and “`;`” semicolon. Each of these tokens is legal, and even though this is not a legal statement, the lexical analyzer detects no error.

The lexical analyzer produces an error message when it encounters a string of characters that do not make a legal token. For example, the character stream `int 5um = 0;` would result in producing the token “`int`” a type, but then stop after reading the “`5u`”. When a token begins with a number, the lexical analyzer is expecting the token to be a number. The occurrence of a non-numeric character in a token that started with a number produces an error message. As seen in the table below, error messages can include ‘a suggestion’ for fixing the code. Often the suggestion is not the right fix to make.

source code	<code>int 5um = 0;</code>
error message	<code>expected identifier or '('</code>
what it means	the character string in the source code is not a legal identifier (i.e., variable name) or another kind of legal phrase that would begin with an open- parenthesis
what to do	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use a legal variable name • DON'T just add parenthesis
source code	<code>int junk@ = 12;</code>
error message	<code>expected ';' at end of declaration</code>
what it means	the character string in the source code is not a legal identifier (i.e., variable name)
what to do	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use a legal variable name • DON'T just add a semi-colon

Like with preprocessor errors, an error detected in the lexical analysis process stops the compilation. As a result, other errors in

the code may not be detected. This can be frustrating when fixing one error seems to produce others.

A.2.3 Semantic Analysis. Source code that passes the preprocessor and lexical analysis stages without error is then scrutinized by the semantic analysis stage of compilation. In semantic analysis, the tokens sequence produced by the lexical analyzer is matched to grammar rules of the programming language. There are many possible ways to violate the grammar rules, and therefore, many possible error messages.

source code	<pre>#include <stdio.h> int main(void) { prxxntf("hello\n"); }</pre>
error message	implicit declaration of function 'prxxntf' is invalid
what it means	the function prxxntf() is undefined (neither in an included library nor defined the defined in the program)
what to do	Spell printf() correctly, or define the function prxxntf()
source code	<pre>#include <stdio.h> int main(void) { print("hello\n"); }</pre>
error message	implicit declaration of function 'print' is invalid. note: did you mean 'printf'?
what it means	the function printf() is undefined (neither in an included library nor defined in the program) However, the compiler recognizes the name printf and makes that suggestion
what to do	Spell printf() correctly, or define the function print()

A.3 General Advice for Responding to Compiler Messages

- Treat all Warnings as if they are errors
- Solve one problem at a time - the one that corresponds to the first compiler message
- Read the compiler message, but take the hints / suggestions with a grain of salt
- If you don't know what an error message means, ask a classmate, or your instructor

B Appendix: Example PEM Lesson 02

Contextual Details:

- Course level/topic: Intro to programming (CS1)
- Prerequisite topics: Basics (assignment and method calls)
- Programming language: Java
- Language version: 20
- Compiler/IDE/Toolchain: IntelliJ IDEA

Lesson elements included:

- The purpose of PEMs
- PEM Structure
- Vocabulary of PEMs
- Resolving Errors
- Under the hood
- Examples of PEMs

Dealing with Error Messages

The Purpose of Error Messages. Programming is a complex task and when doing it you should expect to encounter many error messages. When first learning to program, these messages can be difficult to understand. The important thing to remember is that the purpose of these messages is to **help you** fix the problems that have been identified in your code. They contain information that you can understand and will point you to the source of the problem, if not directly tell you what is wrong.

This is not something that is limited to novice programmers, **experienced programmers frequently encounter errors** when programming. One of the primary differences between novices and experts is that experts have encountered most, if not all of the error messages before and have strategies for understanding the problem and correcting the error. The purpose of this lesson is to help you begin to build strategies for dealing with errors in your own code.

An Error Message Means a Fix is Needed: Error messages are only produced when there is a problem in the code. Compiling or running the same code again without making any changes is pointless and will only result in the exact same error message(s) being produced again.

Programming Errors: Three kinds of errors are made in programming:

- **Syntax Error** - a mistake in the source code of the program that prevents the program from being run (i.e., the program does not conform to the grammar rules of the language). The Java compiler detects syntax errors.
- **Runtime Error** - a running program can encounter errors for a variety of reasons due to bad input, missing files, or other reasons. The Java compiler cannot detect runtime errors. In this case, the program can compile, and run, but does not run successfully (it crashes).
- **Logic Error** - as it says, a mistake in logic. Programs with logical errors can be compiled, but result in a program that does the wrong thing. Java rarely detects logic errors.

This lesson focuses on the first type of error and how we can understand them. As such we will be focusing on the compiler and how errors it finds are presented in the IntelliJ IDEA development environment.

Error Presentation. Consider the image shown in Section B. A portion of the third line of code is highlighted in red. This indicates where the compiler has detected an error in the code. The tooltip that can be accessed by hovering the mouse over the highlighted text gives the message “Cannot resolve symbol ‘O’”. This is the explanation of the error that the compiler has detected. A result of this is that the code we have written cannot be executed.

The problem the compiler has identified is one that is difficult to see when just looking at the code. The letter O (Oscar) has been written in a place that the compiler expected to see a number (we probably meant 0 (zero)).


```

1 public class Example {
2     public static void main(String[] args) {
3         int sum = O;
4     }
5 }
6

```

Solving this error requires understanding the location of the error and the meaning of the message that is presented. Typically, the IDE will locate the problem accurately and will highlight the source of the problem. Unfortunately, this will not always be the case; some searching may be required to find the actual cause. The mistake can be anywhere before the place where the Java compiler detected the error. Often the error location highlighted is after the actual location of the actual error.

Error Presentation. Understanding compiler error messages requires knowing the vocabulary used as well as understanding how errors are detected. Some common error message vocabulary includes:

symbol the name of a variable, class, or method.

resolve understand the meaning of something
<identifier> another name for “symbol”.

expression the combination of values (constants or variables) and operators; for example: $A + B$, or $3.14 * radius * radius$.

statement a variable assignment, a method call, or another statement

illegal invalid or not understood—it does not mean that you broke the law!

The compiler does not know what our program is supposed to do, when it generates an error message it does so only in terms of the source code we have written. This means that error messages can sometimes be misleading. Consider the example above.

The compiler has read the statement and determined that O is a valid name for an identifier (the name for things like methods, variables and classes). So it thinks that O is the name of a variable, but it was not able to find (resolve) any existing identifier with the name O. This is what the error message is trying to convey: “I don’t understand the meaning of O”.

Depending on what we are doing in our code, the solution may be to change it to 0 (zero) if that was what we had intended. In another situation, we may already have a variable named o (lowercase) and we actually wanted to remember the value of that variable.

The Compiler. Turning source code into a running program is a complex problem. The solution to this issue is to separate the task into a number of stages. Each stage completes a part of the process and the result is then used in the next stage and so on until the program is produced. The Java compiler has many stages, but for the purposes of this lesson we will consider the following stages:

- (1) **Lexical analyzer** - reads the source code files as characters and produces **tokens**. A token can be a single variable name, operator, or symbol.
- (2) **Syntactic analyzer** - reads a string of tokens to ensure they follow the syntax (i.e., grammar rules) of the language. For example, it checks that all the curly braces are in the right place, and that all statements end with a semicolon.
- (3) **Semantic analyzer** - checks that all variable names match, checks that the program uses the correct types everywhere, checks that methods that promise to return a value actually do so, etc.

Once Java code has been compiled, it is converted into one or more .class files. These .class files can then be executed by the Java interpreter, called the Java Virtual Machine or JVM. The JVM is where your program runs. If there are any runtime errors, these error messages are generated by the JVM and not from the Java compiler. These errors will be discussed in a later lesson.

Understanding the inner workings of the Java compiler can lead to a better understanding of the error messages that your Java programs might generate. Almost every stage of the process can produce an error message.

Every stage handles a small piece of your program, so none of the stages 'see' your program in full. That means that if you make a mistake, the layer that discovers that mistake probably does not have enough information - or context - to understand exactly what that mistake is. As a result, the error message can be misleading, because the compiler has incomplete information.

Lexical Analysis

The lexical analyzer reads the source code and converts it into tokens. For example, the code `int sum = 0;` would be converted into five tokens:

- (1) `int` - a type
- (2) `sum` - an identifier (variable name)
- (3) `=` - the assignment operator
- (4) `0` - an int constant
- (5) `;` - a semicolon

The rules about what makes a token are complex, but often it is determined by spaces or symbols in the code.

The lexical analyzer produces an error message when it encounters a sequence of characters that it cannot make into a valid token. For example, the code `String name = "Eddie;` would result in the tokens `String`, `name`, and `=`, but then stop because the remaining code cannot be a valid token. The problem is a missing closing quote (`"`), so the Java compiler must produce an error message.

```

Example.java x
1 public class Example {
2     public static void main(String[] args) {
3         String name = "Eddie;
4     }
5 }
Illegal line end in string literal

```

Syntactic Analysis

Syntactic analysis is where the tokens that the lexer has produced are compared to the syntax of the language so the compiler can understand what statements we are using. This is done by a tool known as a parser. The biggest issue faced by the compiler at this stage is that there are often a number of different options available for a sequence of tokens.

Consider a line of code starting with the tokens `int` and `sum`. The statement could potentially be a declaration of a variable, in which case we would expect the next token to be `;`, e.g. `int sum;`. It could be a declaration and assignment together in which case the next token should be `=`, e.g. `int sum = 0;`. Or, it could be the definition of a method in which case the next token would be `(`, e.g. `int sum(int a, int b){`.

```

Example.java x
1 public class Example {
2     public static void main(String[] args) {
3         int sum_numbers = 0;
4     }
5 }
'' expected
Remove local variable 'sum' More actions...
int sum
Errors

```

The image above shows an example where the parser does not know what our intentions are and as such presents an unhelpful error message. In this example, the actual mistake is that spaces cannot be included in variable names, but based on the tokens it has received from the lexer, the parser finds a sequence of tokens that does not make sense. The token `numbers` does not match any of the options it thought we were trying to use, so it tells us it is expecting a semicolon like `;` expected or `class`, `interface` or `enum` expected. In errors similar to this, it is often a good idea to include the preceding lines of code in your search for the problem.

Semantic Analysis

Source code that passes the lexical analysis and syntactical analysis stages without error then moves to the semantic analysis stage. In semantic analysis, a higher level of analysis is applied. The name of every identifier is matched with the value and the types of all operations are all checked to ensure they are correct. The most basic errors that the semantic analysis will discover are typos. Consider the example below:


```

1 public class Example {
2     public static void main(String[] args) {
3         System.out.println('Hello World!');
4     }
5 }

```

Cannot resolve method 'println' in 'PrintStream'

No candidates found for method call System.out.println('Hello World!').

Here we have not typed the name of the method `println` correctly. Similar to the example earlier, the compiler is trying to explain that it cannot match the name we have provided to a method that is available in the `PrintStream` class.


```

1 public class Example {
2     public static void main(String[] args) {
3         int height = 10;
4         System.out.println('Height: ' + height);
5     }
6 }

```

Cannot resolve symbol 'height'

Here we see a very similar message where the name of a variable is not spelled correctly. Again the compiler is trying to tell us that it cannot match the name we have provided to a variable in our class.

The semantic analysis stage also detected errors relating to the correct use of parameters and types. If we are not using the correct number of parameters, we will get an error. If we are not using the correct types, we will get an error.


```

1 public class Example {
2     public static void main(String[] args) {
3         printNumber('12');
4     }
5     public static void printNumber(int number) {
6         System.out.println('Number: ' + number);
7     }
8 }

```

Required type: `int`

Provided: `String`

Here the parameter is highlighted and we are told that the method we are using is expecting an `int`, but we have given it a `String`.


```

public class Example {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int number = 12;
        printNumber();
    }
    public static void printNumber(int number) {
    }
}

```

Expected 1 arguments but found 0

General Advice for Resolving Error Messages.

- Always solve the first error. Many errors will cause your correct code later to appear as an error (particularly syntax errors). Fixing the first error will often resolve many or all of the later errors.
- Read the error message, but do not rely exclusively on the hints / suggestions — they might be wrong
- The line of code that is marked is a good place to start looking for the problem, but sometimes it will be a little above this.
- If you don't know what an error message means, ask a classmate, or your instructor

C Appendix: Survey of Instructors

The following contains the survey distributed to computing instructors.

Survey Title: Teaching Students to Use Programming Error Messages Study

Research Participant Notification:

We invite you to take part in a research study investigating ‘teaching the use of error / warning messages’ to novice programmers. Please read this information carefully. By taking the survey and submitting your responses, you are giving the researchers your formal consent to the collection and use of your data.

Purpose of the research study: Research shows many students struggle to use programming error and warning messages effectively. Instead of using these messages, some students have negative emotional reactions to seeing ‘angry red messages’. Not utilizing compiler messages effectively, or at all, increases the difficulty of learning to program. This survey aims to gain insights into how instructors address error messages in their programming courses.

We would like to invite you to complete this survey, and/or share it across your networks.

This survey is completely anonymous and gathered data will only be used for the purpose of research. The results of this research may be published in professional journals or presented at scientific conferences, but any such presentations will report only aggregated findings, which in some instances may be illustrated by short, anonymous quotes carefully selected so as not to breach individual confidentiality.

Who can take part in the research study: If you teach introductory programming at the collegiate and/or high school level, we invite you to respond to our survey.

What you will be asked to do: If you decide to participate in this research you will be asked to complete a short 5–10 minute online survey about your experience teaching introductory programming. All reported data will be aggregated, and no participant will be identifiable. No individual data will be reported, except for some unidentified quotes from questionnaire answers that will be used to illustrate specific findings. You will not be identified in any reports or publications. By completing the survey, you are giving consent to use the data gathered. Your participation is completely voluntary. If you decide to stop participating: You are free to leave the study at any time; if you choose to do so, simply close your browser. Should you withdraw, all gathered responses will be removed. Following submission of this survey, it will become impossible for us to remove your data because we are not collecting any identifying data that will tie you to your responses.

Questions: Please direct questions or comments to: Dr. Ellie Lovellette (lovelletteeb@cofc.edu | College of Charleston) or Dr. Dennis Bouvier (djb@acm.org | Air Force Academy) or Dr. Brett Becker (brett.becker@ucd.ie | University College Dublin) or Mr. Eddie Antonio Santos (eddie.santos@ucdconnect.ie | University College Dublin)

If you have any ethical concerns about your participation in this research, you may also contact Research Protections & Compliance in the Office of Research and Grants Administration, at 843-953-5885 or e-mail compliance@cofc.edu if you have questions or concerns

about research review at the College of Charleston or your rights as a research participant. College of Charleston IRB file#2023-09-001.

Consent Decision Completion of the survey beyond this section indicates your agreement to this statement of informed consent. To begin the survey, please scroll down.

Questions:

- (1) What programming language(s) do you teach (or are used in introductory programming courses)?
 - Python
 - Java
 - C++
 - other (free response item)
- (2) What level do you teach?
 - CS0 (non-majors or high-school)
 - CS1
 - CS2
 - other (free response item)
- (3) What IDE / compiler / environment is used? (free response item)
- (4) Does your course textbook (or other published educational materials) have an ‘error message reading’ (or similar) material chapter / section / lesson / appendix?
 - Yes No Not sure
- (5) Do you explicitly teach ‘error message reading / understanding’ in your course (i.e., do you have a unit / lesson on ‘how to read error messages’)?
 - Yes No
- (6) If so, briefly list important topics in the unit / lesson and/or provide a link to materials you’d be willing to share. (free response item)
- (7) If not, could ‘reading error messages’ be a good addition to your course? (explain) What are the barriers, if any, to doing so? (free response item)
- (8) Do you think that LLMs (like ChatGPT/Github Copilot) will render compiler error messages (and their associated difficulties) moot?
 - Yes No Not sure
- (9) If so, please explain (free response item)
- (10) Do you teach any other ‘unconventional aspects of programming’, which would be topics not directly listed in ACM curriculum, and/or a non-textbook topic (e.g., programming error messages, version control systems, etc.)?
 - Yes No
- (11) What other ‘unconventional aspects of programming’ do you teach? (free response item)
- (12) How much of a barrier do you think error messages are in terms of learning programming for your students?
 - An insurmountable barrier
 - A big barrier
 - No more or less a barrier than other barriers
 - A small barrier
 - No barrier at all
- (13) What do you see are the biggest barriers presented to students by compiler error messages? (free response item)

D Appendix: Survey of Students

The following contains the survey distributed to students.

Survey Title: Error Messages and You

Research Participant Notification: This short survey is asking about your experience with programming and how you deal with programming error messages when you encounter them. The survey is completely anonymous and the answers you provide here will have no effect on your grade.

Questions:

- (1) What is the course you are currently taking this survey in (e.g. CS 140, CSCI 220 etc.)? (free response item)
- (2) What IDE / compiler / environment are you personally using for this course? (PyCharm, Jupyter Notebooks, BlueJ, Eclipse, Netbeans, VS Code, etc.) (free response item)
- (3) Before this course, how much prior programming experience did you have
 - None
 - Very little (0–3 months)
 - Some (3–6 months)
 - A good deal (6–12 months)
 - A lot (1–2 years)
 - Extensive (2+ years)
- (4) What do you feel is your level of proficiency with programming
 - Complete novice — just learning programming now for the first time
 - Advanced beginner — some prior experience with programming, but not too much
 - Competent — I can write simple programs
 - Proficient — I can write more complex programs
 - Expert — I can write any program
- (5) When you are working on code and you see an error message, what is your usual reaction? (select all that apply)
 - Panic, I don't know what to do with this and I don't understand it
 - I completely ignore it and continue writing code hoping for the best
 - I ignore the actual message but look for the line it tells me I have a problem
 - I read the message but I don't always understand what it means
 - I read the message and try to understand what it's telling me
 - I read the message and try to understand what the problem is and on what line
 - I read the message and follow the suggested fix
- (6) When you are dealing with an error message, where are you most likely to seek help? (select all that apply)
 - Nowhere, I just keep trying things and see what works
 - Nowhere, I read the message and try to use it to fix the problem
 - Nowhere, the programming environment tells me exactly what I need to do to fix it
 - I look in the textbook
- I Google it and look for an explanation of what the error message means
- I Google it and follow the links to forums like StackOverflow looking for fixes that worked for others
- I ask my Instructor / Professor
- I ask my Teaching Assistant / Tutor
- I ask my classmates
- I ask my more experienced friends
- I ask A.I. like ChatGPT, Github Copilot etc.

(7) How do you feel about programming error messages in general? (free response item)

E Appendix: Experiment Survey

The following contains the survey distributed to students during the PEM Experiment.

Survey Title: Programming Error Messages and You

Research Participant Notification: This survey is asking about your experience with programming error messages and how you deal with programming error messages when you encounter them.

You must be post-secondary college students who is 17 years or older to participate. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time. Completion of the survey constitutes your consent to participate in this research. All data obtained will be anonymous and the answers you provide here will have no effect on your grade. We ask that you do not provide any information that could identify you personally. The data collected for this research will be stored until the research study associated with it is published.

If you have any questions concerning this research study, please contact Dr. Ellie Lovellette lovelletteeb@cofc.edu. This research has been reviewed by the Human Research Protection Program at the College of Charleston and covers all relevant requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulations. For information about the review process, please contact the Office of Research and Grants Administration, compliance@cofc.edu or 843-953-5885.

We expect the survey will take 15-17 minutes to complete. if you wish to participate, proceed to questionnaire by answering the first question.

Section 1: Pre-Lesson Questions

Complete the questions in this section only and stop until your teacher tells you to continue. Don't close this window.

- (1) What is the course you are currently taking this survey in (e.g. CS 140, CSCI 220 etc.)? (free response item)
- (2) What IDE / compiler / environment are you personally using for this course? (PyCharm, Jupyter Notebooks, BlueJ, Eclipse, Netbeans, VS Code, etc.) (free response item)
- (3) Before this course, how much prior programming experience did you have
 - None
 - Very little (0–3 months)
 - Some (3–6 months)
 - A good deal (6–12 months)
 - A lot (1–2 years)
 - Extensive (2+ years)
- (4) What do you feel is your level of proficiency with programming
 - Complete novice — just learning programming now for the first time
 - Advanced beginner — some prior experience with programming, but not too much
 - Competent — I can write simple programs
 - Proficient — I can write more complex programs
 - Expert — I can write any program
- (5) When you are working on code and you see an error message, what is your usual reaction? (select all that apply)
 - Panic, I don't know what to do with this and I don't understand it

- I completely ignore it and continue writing code hoping for the best
 - I ignore the actual message but look for the line it tells me I have a problem
 - I read the message but I don't always understand what it means
 - I read the message and try to understand what it's telling me
 - I read the message and try to understand what the problem is and on what line
 - I read the message and follow the suggested fix
- (6) When you are dealing with an error message, where are you most likely to seek help? (select all that apply)
 - Nowhere, I just keep trying things and see what works
 - Nowhere, I read the message and try to use it to fix the problem
 - Nowhere, the programming environment tells me exactly what I need to do to fix it
 - I look in the textbook
 - I Google it and look for an explanation of what the error message means
 - I Google it and follow the links to forums like StackOverflow looking for fixes that worked for others
 - I ask my Instructor / Professor
 - I ask my Teaching Assistant / Tutor
 - I ask my classmates
 - I ask my more experienced friends
 - I ask A.I. like ChatGPT, Github Copilot etc.
 - (7) How do you feel about programming error messages in general? (free response item)

Stop until your teacher tells you to continue. Don't close this window.

Section 2: Video Lesson Questions

Please answer the following questions after you've seen the video lesson shown in class and then stop until your teacher tells you to continue. Don't close this window.

- (8) The Programming Error Messages *video lesson* was easy to understand
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
- (9) The Programming Error Messages *video lesson* contained
 - A lot of information new to me
 - Some information new to me
 - Little information new to me
 - No information new to me
- (10) The Programming Error Messages *video lesson* was useful
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree

	Saw in the video but did NOT know from before	Knew from before but did NOT see in the video	Both saw in the video AND knew from before	
(11) The Programming Error Messages <i>video lesson</i> was enjoyable				Saw in the video but did NOT know from before
○ Strongly Agree				
○ Agree				
○ Neutral				
○ Disagree				
○ Strongly disagree				
(12) Was there anything is particular you liked about the Programming Error Messages <i>video lesson</i> ? (free response item)				Some error messages contain suggestions for a fix
(13) Of the points below, select which ones you knew before and/or which ones you heard in the Programming Error Messages video lesson				All error message suggestions for a fix should be considered unreliable
				If you don't understand an error message, you can look it up online to find out what it means
				If you don't understand an error message, you can look it up online and follow links to forums like StackOverflow to see how other people dealt with the same message
All programmers make mistakes, it's normal	○	○	○	If you don't understand an error message, you can ask AI (like ChatGPT) to explain the message
Error messages make you aware of problems with the code	○	○	○	Use both the source code and error message when prompting AI like ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, etc.
Error messages are not personal	○	○	○	AI can be wrong about error message explanations
Error messages are intended to be helpful	○	○	○	If you don't understand an error message, you can ask other people (classmates, friends, teacher)
Error messages are the result of code that doesn't follow language rules	○	○	○	(14) Was there something you didn't see in the Programming Error Messages video lesson but wish it was included? (free response item)
Some IDEs provide red underlining to indicate errors	○	○	○	Stop until your teacher tells you to continue. Don't close this window.
Some errors are simpler to fix than others	○	○	○	<i>Section 3: Exercise Questions</i>
Many error messages may be displayed at one time	○	○	○	Answer two questions after each program you successfully compile. <u>Don't close this window.</u>
Multiple error messages may be caused by the same error	○	○	○	(15) Where was (were) the error(s) in <i>Program 1</i> ? (free response item)
It's a good strategy to start by fixing the very first error and recompiling	○	○	○	(16) How did you find the error(s) in <i>Program 1</i> ? How easy was the problem to find and fix? (free response item)
Messages may be errors or warnings	○	○	○	(17) Where was (were) the error(s) in <i>Program 2</i> ? (free response item)
All warnings should be taken as seriously as errors	○	○	○	(18) How did you find the error(s) in <i>Program 2</i> ? How easy was the problem to find and fix? (free response item)
Error messages usually contain a line number	○	○	○	(19) Where was (were) the error(s) in <i>Program 3</i> ? (free response item)
If the error message contains a line number the error can be on that line	○	○	○	
If the error message contains a line number the error can be above that line	○	○	○	

- (20) How did you find the error(s) in *Program 3*? How easy was the problem to find and fix? (free response item)
- (21) Where was (were) the error(s) in *Program 4*? (free response item)
- (22) How did you find the error(s) in *Program 4*? How easy was the problem to find and fix? (free response item)
- (23) Where was (were) the error(s) in *Program 5*? (free response item)
- (24) How did you find the error(s) in *Program 5*? How easy was the problem to find and fix? (free response item)

If you're done with the exercises, continue to Sections 4 and 5 (only 6 more questions) and complete the survey.

Section 4: Exercise Activity Questions

Answer the questions about all the activities you completed.

- (24) The Programming Error Messages *activity* was
- Very easy
 - Easy
 - Neither easy nor difficult
 - Difficult
 - Very Difficult
- (25) The Programming Error Messages *activity* was useful
- Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
- (26) The Programming Error Messages *activity* was enjoyable
- Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree

Section 5: Post-Lesson Questions

When you answer the questions, hit submit. Thank you for participating.

- (27) *After this Programming Error Messages lesson* (video lesson and activity), *in the future*, when you are working on code and you see an error message, what do you expect your reaction will be? (select all that apply)
- Panic, I don't know what to do with this and I don't understand it
 - I completely ignore it and continue writing code hoping for the best
 - I ignore the actual message but look for the line it tells me I have a problem
 - I read the message but I don't always understand what it means
 - I read the message and try to understand what it's telling me
 - I read the message and try to understand what the problem is and on what line
 - I read the message and follow the suggested fix
- (28) *After this Programming Error Messages lesson* (video lesson and activity), *in the future*, when you are dealing with an

error message, where do you expect you will be most likely to seek help? (select all that apply)

- Nowhere, I just keep trying things and see what works
 - Nowhere, I read the message and try to use it to fix the problem
 - Nowhere, the programming environment tells me exactly what I need to do to fix it
 - I look in the textbook
 - I Google it and look for an explanation of what the error message means
 - I Google it and follow the links to forums like StackOverflow looking for fixes that worked for others
 - I ask my Instructor / Professor
 - I ask my Teaching Assistant / Tutor
 - I ask my classmates
 - I ask my more experienced friends
 - I ask A.I. like ChatGPT, Github Copilot etc.
- (29) *After this Programming Error Messages lesson* (video lesson and activity), how I feel about error messages *now* is.. (free response item)

F Appendix: Experiment Ability Items in C

The following contains the ability items in the C language distributed to students during the PEM Experiment and their corresponding error messages.

Program 1

```
// FILE: program01.c
#include <stdio.h>

int main(int argc, char* argv[]){

    int value

    printf("enter a number: ");
    scanf("%i", &value);

    printf("the number entered: %d.\n", value);

    return 0;
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 1

```
program01.c:7:14: error: expected ';' at end of declaration
    int value
      ^
    ;
1 error generated.
```

Program 2

```
// FILE: program02.c
#include <stdio.h>

int main(int argc, char* argv[]){

    int a = 10;
    int b = 20;
    int c = 0;

    a + b = c;

    printf("the sum is %d.\n", c);

    return 0;
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 2

```
program02.c:11:11: error: expression is not assignable
    a + b = c;
      ~~~~ ^
1 error generated.
```

Program 3

```
// FILE: program03.c
#include <stdio.h>

int main(int argc, char* argv[])

    float length = 12.1;
    float width = 23.2;

    float area = length * width;

    printf("the area is %f.\n", area);

    return 0;
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 3

```
program03.c:5:33: error: expected ';' after top level declarator
int main(int argc, char* argv[])
      ^
    ;
program03.c:10:24: error: initializer element is not a compile-time constant
    float area = length * width;
                  ~~~~~^~~~~~
program03.c:12:11: error: expected parameter declarator
    printf("the area is %f.\n", area);
      ^
program03.c:12:11: error: expected ')'
program03.c:12:10: note: to match this '('
    printf("the area is %f.\n", area);
      ^
program03.c:12:4: warning: type specifier missing, defaults to 'int' [-Wimplicit-int]
    printf("the area is %f.\n", area);
      ^
program03.c:12:4: error: conflicting types for 'printf'
/Applications/Xcode.app/Contents/Developer/Platforms/MacOSX.platform/Developer/SDKs/MacOSX.sdk/usr/include/stdio.h:170:6: note: previous declaration is here
int printf(const char * __restrict, ...) __printflike(1, 2);
      ^
program03.c:14:4: error: expected identifier or '('
    return 0;
      ^
program03.c:15:1: error: extraneous closing brace ('}')
}
^
1 warning and 7 errors generated.
```


G Appendix: Experiment Ability Items in Java

The following contains the ability items in the Java language distributed to students during the PEM Experiment and their corresponding error messages. Absolute paths in error messages omitted for generality. Statements in Programs 1, 4 and 5 broken into multiple lines for formatting purposes appeared on a single line in the original source code.

Program 1

```
//FILE: Program01.java

import java.util.Scanner;

public class Program01 {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Scanner keyboard = new Scanner(System.in);
        int value

        System.out.print("Enter a number: ");
        value = keyboard.nextInt();

        System.out.printf("The number entered: %d.\n",
            value);
    }
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 1

```
.. \Program01.java:6:18
java: ';' expected
```

Program 2

```
//FILE: Program02.java

public class Program02 {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int a = 10;
        int b = 20;
        int c = 0;

        a + b = c;

        System.out.printf("The sum is %d.\n", c);
    }
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 2

```
.. \Program02.java:7:11
java: unexpected type
   required: variable
   found:    value
```

Program 3

```
//FILE: Program03.java

public class Program03 {
    public static void main(String[] args)
        double length = 12.1;
        double width = 23.2;

        double area = length * width;

        System.out.printf("the area is %f.\n", area);
    }
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 3

```
.. \Program03.java:2:43
java: ';' expected
.. \Program03.java:8:26
java: <identifier> expected
.. \Program03.java:8:27
java: illegal start of type
.. \Program03.java:10
java: class, interface, enum, or record expected
```

Program 4

```
//FILE: Program04.java

public class Program04 {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        int x = 10, y = 15, temp;

        System.out.printf("Original values: x = %d
            and y = %d.\n", x, y);

        temp = x;
        x = y;
        y = temp;

        System.out.printf("Swapped values: x = %d
            and y = %d.\n", x, y);
    }
}
```

Error Messages Associated with Program 4

```
.. \Program04.java:5:45
java: ')' expected
.. \Program04.java:5:50
java: illegal start of expression
.. \Program04.java:5:52
java: ';' expected
.. \Program04.java:5:61
java: illegal start of expression
.. \Program04.java:5:64
java: illegal character: '\'
```

```

..\Program04.java:5:65
java: not a statement
..\Program04.java:5:66
java: ';' expected
..\Program04.java:5:68
java: not a statement
..\Program04.java:5:69
java: ';' expected
..\Program04.java:5:71
java: not a statement
..\Program04.java:5:72
java: ';' expected

```

```

..\Program05.java:10:37
java: incompatible types: possible lossy conversion from
double to float
..\Program05.java:20:31
java: cannot find symbol
symbol:   variable 0
location: class Program05
..\Program05.java:26:49
java: cannot find symbol
symbol:   variable area
location: class Program05

```

----- **Program 5** -----

```

//FILE: Program05.java

import java.util.Scanner;

public class Program05 {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Scanner keyboard = new Scanner(System.in);

        float length = 0;

        System.out.printf("Enter a length: ");
        length = keyboard.nextDouble();

        double triArea = 0;
        triArea = length * 0.5 * length;
        System.out.printf("Triangle area: %f\n", triArea);

        double squareArea = 0;
        squareArea = length * length;
        System.out.printf("Square area: %f\n", squareArea);

        double pentagonArea = 0;
        pentagonArea = 1.72048 * length * length;
        System.out.printf("Pentagon area: %f\n", pentagonArea);

        double hexArea = 0;
        hexArea = 2.59808 * length * length;
        System.out.printf("Hexagon area: %f\n", area);

    }
}

```

----- **Error Messages Associated with Program 5** -----